

Operation *Galugad*: ELT-infused glocalized module on experiential learning

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Abstract

Amidst social distancing issues in times of the COVID-19 pandemic, modular learning offers the best strategy to overcome problems in the delivery of instruction. Aimed to determine the effectiveness of the developed glocalized experiential learning-infused module in Earth and Life Science. Experiential learning is theorized to improve students' mastery of science competencies. Using quasi-experimental research, pretest-posttest design, the participants are the Grade 11 students of Libacao National Forestry Vocational High School (LNFVHS), the school year 2019-2020. Data came from the module's posttests and the Student Evaluation of Learning Experience Questionnaire (SELEQ). The learning material consisted of a glocalized print module and its video-based accompaniment. Results of SELEQ and Posttest revealed a significant increase after using the module. Correlation analysis of SELEQ and Posttest revealed a significant positive linear relationship. Hence, when learning materials are glocalized, infused with experiential learning activities, learners are more likely to be engaged, improving their academic performance.

Keywords: *experiential learning, glocalization, learner's material, video-based module*

Introduction

COVID-19, which was identified in December 2019, quickly became a global pandemic. This health pandemic has utterly disrupted an education system that, many assert, is already losing its relevance. Social distancing and mass gathering protocols have affected the traditional teaching methods. Amidst this pandemic, distance education using print and non-print learning materials offers opportunities to continue education. This study focused on using the validated Experiential Learning Theory (ELT)-enriched, and glocalized module in Earth and Life Science.

The Philippines ranked in the low 70s in the 2018 Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA), a student assessment of 15-year-old learners across 79 countries done by the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD). The Philippines ranked last among 79 countries in reading comprehension, mathematics, and science (Paris, 2019). The National Achievement Test (NAT) results of the students in the Division of Aklan revealed that the Science and Math scores are the lowest among the assessed subjects (DepEd, 2019). Science is a subject best learned through hands-on and actual experience. It has been observed that the students lack this aspect of learning. The module created by the researcher is rooted in Experiential Learning Theory which emphasizes that students best understand and retain the topics through experiences.

Republic Act No. 10533, made into law last May 15, 2013, states that

“The DepEd shall adhere to the following standards and principles in developing the enhanced basic education curriculum: ... (d) The curriculum shall be contextualized and global” (Official Gazzette, 2013).

To address this demand, the researcher opted to make this research-based learning resource.

Glocalization is the simultaneous occurrence of universalizing and particularizing tendencies in contemporary social, political, and economic systems. The term is a linguistic hybrid of globalization and localization popularized by Roland Robertson, a sociologist (Rouse, 2018). The learning module that this study developed followed the same principle: localized to the learners in the Philippines and tailored to the global learners.

'*Galugad*' is a Tagalog term that translates to '*exploration*.' The activity-based instructions in the module were infused with experiential learning that accommodated differentiated learning. The module that was created and developed by the researcher (Nagal, 2020) contained learning activities that encourage the learner to explore ('*galugad*') his surroundings and relate them to the concepts, hence, the title '*Operation Galugad*.'

These arguments are only a few pieces of evidence that learning material is necessary for conducting daily classroom activities. The study focused on the effectiveness of the developed ELT-enriched glocalized module in Earth and Life Science, specifically the competencies in Bioenergetics, to enhance students' experiential learning and improve academic performance.

More specifically, the researcher answered the following research questions:

1. What are the contents of the developed Learner's Materials and its video accompaniment?
2. What is the students' experiential learning level before and after exposure to the module?
3. Is there a significant difference in the students' experiential learning level before and after exposure to the module?
4. What is the students' performance in Bioenergetics before and after the intervention?
5. Is there a significant difference between the students' performance in Bioenergetics before and after the intervention?
6. Is there a significant relationship between the student's experiential learning level and academic performance?

Methodology

Research design

This study used quasi-experimental research, specifically pretest-posttest design. The study treated data quantitatively focusing on the results of the Student Evaluation of Learning Experience Questionnaire (SELEQ) and the students' performance in Bioenergetics.

Selection criteria and sources of data

The participants of this study were the Grade 11 students of Libacao National Forestry Vocational High School, SY 2019-2020. The respondents for the SELEQ and posttest were chosen randomly from the population size of 141 students at a 95% confidence level. One hundred four students answered the tools before and after the interventions.

Data analysis

The data from the SELEQ and posttest were the basis of the effectiveness of the interventions. SELEQ was used to evaluate the experiential learning levels of students. The posttest was used to evaluate learning performance in Bioenergetics. The data were collected before and after using the module, and analyzed using descriptive (mean, standard deviation) and inferential (t-test, Pearson's r) statistics. A Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 2.0 software was used to compute the data.

Findings

Contents of the learner's material and its video-accompaniment

The Learner's Material was developed from the least-mastered competencies in Bioenergetics: The Cell, Photosynthetic Reactions, and Acquisition and Utilization of Energy. Globalization and experiential learning were the focus in developing the globalized experiential learning-infused module in Earth and Life Science.

Glocalization in the learning materials is integrated through the use of Mother Tongue (Akeanon) in the video-based module, localized and indigenized materials used in the experimentations and other experiential learning activities, and a universal language (English) in both the module and video subtitle. The use of varied activities emphasizing experiential learning, multiple intelligences, and differentiated strategies were incorporated in the elaboration and extension parts of the module. The use of gadgets, software, and videos integrates ICT in the module. The cover and chapter design of print materials were originally crafted by the researcher. Pictures and contents taken from public domains were properly cited in the references. The rest of the standards were taken from D.O. #411, s. 2018 (DepEd Division of Aklan, 2018). Table 1 shows the major features of the learning module and its video accompaniment.

Table 1.
Major features of the learner’s module and the video accompaniment

Features	Learner’s Module	Video accompaniment
<i>Cover Page</i>		
<i>About the Developer’s Page / Introductory Video</i>	<p style="text-align: center;">ABOUT THE DEVELOPER</p> <p>Raphael Kevin Nagal y Inguin was born on October 24, 1986 at Madalag, Aklan. His parents are Dioleto Nagal y Nasaral and Teodora Inguin y Naig. He is the fourth child among the five siblings. Nicknamed as "Nono" within the family circle, he was commonly called by his second given name.</p> <p>Kevin took his elementary diploma as the First Honors of his batch at Madalag Elementary School. He was also the Class Valedictorian during his time at Madalag National High School. He passed the University of the Philippines College</p>	
<i>Title Page / Graphic Introduction</i>		

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<p>Knowledge Checker / Graphic Illustrations</p>	<p>Diagram illustrating the process of photosynthesis in a chloroplast. Light energy enters the Light Dependent Reaction, which produces ATP and NADPH. These energy carriers then move to the Light Independent Reaction (Calvin Cycle), where CO₂ is fixed into C₆H₁₂O₆ (glucose). O₂ is released as a byproduct.</p>	
<p>Experimentations / Experiential Learning Activities</p>	<p>LET'S ENHANCE YOUR LEARNING: Check to Check...</p> <p>Experiment A: All living plants and animals are made up of some combination of cells! There are various kinds of, such as connective, epithelial, muscle, and nervous cells, which grow together as tissue! Nervous tissue, connective tissue, and muscle tissue are, unfortunately, hard to examine up close without an invasive procedure. Fortunately, epithelial cells are available in abundance from your very own mouth for external examination! The epithelial cells we'll be examining in this experiment are from the inside of your cheek and are specifically classified as "Stratified Squamous Nonkeratinized Epithelium."</p> <p>Materials: toothpick; Water; tissue paper; microscope and slide; cellphone camera</p> <p>Procedure:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Place a drop of water on the slide. <p>LET'S MEASURE YOUR LEARNING! MULTIPLE CHOICE. Encircle the letter of the correct answer.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Which of the following is FALSE about photosynthesis? a. The main product of photosynthesis is carbon dioxide. c. Photosynthesis makes use of carbon dioxide to make glucose. b. The main product of photosynthesis is oxygen and glucose. d. Photosynthesis occurs in two stages. 2. Which of the following is TRUE about the Calvin's Cycle? a. Its main process is to convert carbon dioxide to glucose. c. This process occurs in the presence of light energy. b. Oxygen is produced in this stage. d. Carbon dioxide is used independently without the light dependent cycle. 3. Which of the following occurs during the light-dependent reaction? a. Carbon dioxide is converted to glucose. c. Oxygen is dissociated from water through photolysis. b. Oxygen is released into the atmosphere. d. Carbon dioxide is metabolized to form glucose. 4. All of these may happen at any stage of photosynthesis except a. Carbon dioxide is converted to glucose. c. Oxygen is dissociated from water through photolysis. b. Glucose molecules are converted to ATP. d. Oxygen is released into the atmosphere. 5. Chlorophyll is found in special cells in the leaves called a. Membranes b. Chloroplasts c. Pigments d. Roots <p>PLEASE PAUSE UNTIL YOU FINISHED THE TEST</p>	
<p>Assessment</p>	<p>LET'S CHECK YOUR KNOWLEDGE!</p> <p>True or False. Identify whether the following statements is True or False. Write your answers on the space provided before each number.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The cells are the basic unit of life. 2. Meiosis exists only in plant cells. 	

Students' experiential learning level before and after utilizing the module

Table 2 presents the experiential learning level of students based on two episodes of the SELEQ scores. The pretest and posttest were composed of 55-item conditions thought to be part of experiential learning of students in Science.

The pretest (SELEQ1) mean score of students was 2.60, *Moderate Experience Level*. After utilizing the module, the mean score (SELEQ2) improved to 3.51, *High Experience Level*.

Table 2.
Students' Experiential Learning Level Before and After Utilizing the Module

Paired Samples Statistics		Mean	N	Standard Deviation	Standard Error Mean
Pair 1	SELEQ1	2.60	104	0.71079	0.06970
	SELEQ2	3.51	104	0.61062	0.05988

Analysis of paired samples t-test in Table 3 reveals that there was a significant difference (5%) in the students' experiential learning level before and after using the module (t-value=-11.393; p-value=0.000).

Table 3.
Difference in Students' Experiential Learning Level Before and After Utilizing the Module

Paired Samples Test		Paired Differences (N=104)			95% Confidence Interval of the Difference		t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	Lower	Upper				
Pair 1 -	SELEQ1 - SELEQ2	-0.92	0.82	0.08	-1.08	-0.76	-11.393	103	0.000

*significant at 5% level

The results revealed that the experiential learning of students has been dramatically improved from moderate to a high level of experience implying the module's effectiveness.

Performance of students in bioenergetics before and after utilizing the module

Table 4 presents the students' performance on the pretest and posttest scores. The pretest and posttest were composed of a 30-item multiple-choice test.

The test was equally divided into three parts: The Cell, Photosynthetic Reactions, and Acquisition & Utilization of Energy. Before utilizing the module, the mean scores of students for The Cell was 4.52 (*Least Mastered*), the Photosynthetic Reactions was 3.90 (*Least Mastered*), and Acquisition & Utilization of Energy was 4.36 (*Least Mastered*). After utilizing the Learner's Material, the mean scores improved to 7.35 (*Satisfactorily Mastered*), 7.04 (*Satisfactorily Mastered*), 6.79 (*Satisfactorily Mastered*), respectively. All scores have increased by 2-3 points on average.

Table 4.
Performance of Students in Bioenergetics Before and After the Utilization of the Module

	Mean Scores (N = 104)			
	The Cell	Photosynthetic Reactions	Acquisition and Utilization of Energy	Average
Pretest	4.52	3.90	4.36	12.78
Posttest	7.35	7.04	6.79	21.17
Difference	2.83	3.14	2.43	8.39

Analysis of paired samples t-test in Table 5 revealed that there was a significant difference (5%) in the students' performance in Bioenergetics before and after the utilization of the module (t -value=-4.731; p -value=0.000).

The results revealed that the students' performance in Bioenergetics improved using the module and its video accompaniment. Their scores were upped to Satisfactorily Mastered levels, implying that using the module has improved their learning experience and in turn, enhanced their performance in Bioenergetics.

Table 5.
Difference in the Performance of Students Before and After the Utilization of the Module

Paired Samples Statistics									
		Mean	N	Standard Deviation	Standard Error Mean				
Pair 1	POSTTEST1	12.78	104	5.06071	0.49624				
	POSTTEST2	21.17	104	3.07651	0.30168				
Paired Samples Test									
Paired Differences (N=104)									
		Mean	Standard Deviation	Standard Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference		T	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
					Lower	Upper			
Pair 1	POSTTEST1 POSTTEST2	-8.39	6.18	0.61	-9.596	-7.193	-13.857	103	0.000

*significant at 5% level

Relationship between the learning experience level and performance in bioenergetics of students before and after the utilization of the module

Analysis of Pearson's r correlation test in Table 6 reveals that there was a significant relationship (5%) between the Learning Experience Level and Performance in Bioenergetics of students (p-value=0.000).

Table 6.
Relationship Between the Learning Experience Level and Performance in Bioenergetics of Students Before and After the Utilization of the Module

Correlations		SELEQ	POSTTEST
SELEQ	Pearson Correlation	1	0.379**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.000
	N	208	208
POSTTEST	Pearson Correlation	0.379**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	
	N	208	208

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Further analysis of the correlation test in Figure 1 shows that there is a significant (1%) positive linear relationship (r -value=+1) between the two variables. That is, the higher the Learning Experience Level of students, the higher their Performance are in Bioenergetics.

Figure 1.

Scatterplot of Relationship Between Learning Experience Level of Students and their Performance in Bioenergetics

These data further proved the premise that enhancing experiential learning also improves student performance at school. Thus, using globalized experiential-learning-infused modules greatly helps in achieving the goals of a learning competency.

Discussions and conclusions

When learning materials are glocalized, contextualized, and infused with experiential learning activities, learners are more likely to be engaged in learning the concepts. Furthermore, the conversational manner of teaching, as well as the use of varied learning materials to supplement traditional teaching methods is proven to enhance understanding of the topics. Lastly, the videos accompanying the module are the best response to the 21st-century learners who are more visual when it comes to learning. The experiential learning level of a student is directly related to his performance in a competency. Thus, to enhance student performance in Science and any other subjects, experiential learning must be taken into consideration. The module helps in encouraging independent and supplemental learning in all grade levels.

Recommendations

It is highly recommended that the module and its video accompaniment used in this research be utilized in other areas. Textbook developers must also ensure that the learning materials they create are easy to understand and contain varied activities for the benefit of the learners.

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